

Designing Ethics Automation Projects to Increase the Odds of Research Success

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Ethical reasoning research projects have to realistically set the scope of their objectives. If we want to automate ethical reasoning, we will either find ourselves picking and choosing among many approaches or collapsing several of them together into a smaller set of methods. We will discuss some of these trade-offs in this talk.

People derive ethical systems in a variety of ways. These systems may be manufactured using values, norms, or the behavior of exemplary people. Ethical systems may also be structured from sets of rules collected and tuned over time, then passed down from authorities.

Sometimes, ethical judgments are best made through analysis of utility functions, benefit-cost, and aggregate social well-being. Ethical decisions also emerge from political processes that are seen as worth preserving, even if some of the results are deeply flawed, or even deadly.

Some AI methods are a mismatch with some of the ways ethical systems may emerge. Therefore, research projects have to limit themselves to specific pairings.

We also have to distinguish between engineering away deadly and destructive errors and automating ethics. People frequently take action which results in disastrous negative outcomes because they are mistaken about facts or are endangering people's lives with a flawed physical process. Trying to design an ethical reasoning system that corrects every dangerous mistake people make is beyond the scope of a plausible engineering effort. Many kinds of reasoning errors that lead to bad outcomes are not errors in ethical reasoning.

Even after peeling away these layers, the scope of ethics automation remains far too large to address practically. For this reason, we will discuss how to specify smaller efforts that can create demonstrations and examples of automated ethical reasoning which can accomplish something useful, meaningful, or illustrative. Some of these efforts may be generalizable. Others will not. In the early stages, we should not be concerned if we don't solve the whole problem. Tangible, but more modest results are easier to discuss, critique, refine, and expand.

Finally, we have to choose specific software development, AI tools, and packages. We can expect the performance of some of these tools to improve by more than 10,000% over the next ten years. Others will improve, but more slowly. We might be willing to begin with software that currently seems slow or lacks functionality if we can forecast improvement over time.

This research began in conjunction with members of the AI group at SRI International.